

PERISTALTIC FLOW OF A COUPLE STRESS FLUID IN A FLEXIBLE CHANNEL UNDER AN OSCILLATORY FLUX

S. Ravikumar¹, G. Prabhakar Rao², and R. Siva Prasad²

¹*Department of Mathematics, N.B.K.R. Institute of Science and Technology, Vidya Nagar, Nellore, Andhra Pradesh-524413, India*

Email: drsravikumar1979@gmail.com

²*Department of Mathematics, Sri Krishna Devaraya University, Anantapur, Andhra Pradesh-515003, India*

Received 10 August 2009; accepted 21 November 2009

ABSTRACT

In this paper we have analyzed the flow of a couple stress fluids in a channel bounded by flexible walls over which a traveling wave of contraction and expansion is imposed resulting in a peristaltic motion. An oscillatory time dependent flow is also imposed on this flow. The non-linear equations governing the flow through porous medium are solved under long wavelength approximation. The existence of separation in the flow field is discussed for different values of the governing parameterers. The streamlines are plotted to discuss to phenomenon of trapping and reflex. The behavior of the primary and secondary velocity components, the shear stresses on the wall, the time average fluxes have been analyzed in either case for different sets of parameters.

Keywords: Couple stress fluids, Peristaltic motion, the time average fluxes, Reynolds number

1 INTRODUCTION

Fluid transportation can take place in a channel or pipe with flexible walls by imposing a wave of contraction or expansion propagating along its length. This type of flow is usually referred as peristaltic flow and it is one of the major mechanisms for fluid transportation in any biological system. The mechanism of peristaltic transport has been exploited for industrial applications like sanitary fluid transport, blood pumps in heart lung machine and transport of corrosive fluids where the contact of the fluid with the machinery parts is prohibited. A vast amount of literature is available on the peristaltic involving viscous fluid under one or more assumption(s) of long wavelength, small Reynold number, small amplitude ratio, small wave number etc. by Abd El Hakeem Abd El Naby *et al.* (Abd El Hakeem Abd El Naby *et al.* 2006), El Shehawey *et al.* (El Shehawey *et al.* 1994), Eldabe *et al.* (Eldabe *et al.* 2007), Hayat and Ali (Hayat and Ali 2006) , Hayat *et al.* (Hayat *et al.* 2007), Hayat and Masood Khan *et al.* (Hayat and Masood Khan *et al.* 2007), Hayat and Wang *et al.* (Hayat and Wang *et al.* 2002), Mekhmer Kh.S (Mekhmer Kh.S 2003), Mekhmer Kh.S (Mekhmer Kh.S 2003), Mekhmer Kh.S and Al-Arabi (Mekhmer Kh.S and Al-Arabi 2003), Mekhmer Kh.S and El Shehawey *et al.* (Mekhmer Kh.S and El Shehawey *et al.* 1998), Ramachandra and Usha

(Ramachandra and Usha 2003), Shapirio and Jaffrin *et al.* (Shapirio and Jaffrin *et al.* 1969), Srivastava (Srivastava 1986), Srivastava and Saxena (Srivastava and Saxena 1995), Tsiklauri and Beresnev (Tsiklauri and Beresnev 2001), Vajravelu and Sreenadh *et al.* (Vajravelu and Sreenadh *et al.* 2005). Since the first investigation of Latham (Latham 1966), several theoretical and experimental attempts have been made to understand peristaltic action in different situations. The earlier mathematical work on the problem of peristaltic transport was based upon a viscous fluid modal governed by the Navier-Stokes equations subjected to prescribed velocity on the boundary of the tube. All important literature up to 1978 on peristaltic transport has been documented by Rath (Rath 1980). Fung and Yih (Fung and Yih 1969) analyzed the role of Reynolds number and wavelength in peristaltic motion of moderate amplitude, making use of perturbation method with an amplitude ratio as the perturbation parameter. Burns and Parkes (Burns and Parkes 1967) have discussed the peristaltic flow produced by sinusoidal peristaltic wave along flexible walls of a channel under the pressure gradient. Latham and Shapiro (Latham and Shapiro 1966), Fung and Yih (Fung and Yih 1969), Boyarsky *et al.* (Boyarsky *et al.* 1971) have investigated this phenomenon using different configurations. Also a number of recent investigations have reported the pulsatile nature of blood flow in pulmonary arteries and different portions of mesentery. Rappaport *et al.* (Rappaport *et al.* 1959) on pulmonary arteries and measurements by Gachtgens (Gachtgens 1970) and Intaglietta (Intaglietta 1971) show conclusively that the pulsatile flow exists throughout the microcirculation of blood. Thus the realistic modal of the blood flow in the smaller vessels must include pulsatile flow effects in addition to the peristaltic flow created by the motion of the flexible boundary. Wilson and Perel (Wilson and Perel 1979) have studied the peristaltic motion for a two dimensional channel when the initial flow is pulsatile. Also the interaction of poiseuille flow on the peristaltic motion has been discussed by Mitra and Prasad (Mitra and Prasad 1974). More recently, Mishra and Ramachandra Rao (Mishra and Ramachandra Rao 2003) have investigated the flow in an asymmetric channel generated by peristaltic waves propagating on the walls with different amplitudes and phases. The interaction of peristaltic flow with pulsatile fluid in a circular cylindrical tube is studied by Srivastava and Srivastava (Srivastava and Srivastava 1988).

2 FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

We consider a peristaltic flow of a couple stress fluids in a symmetric channel with flexible walls, which are excited by a traveling longitudinal wave resulting in a peristaltic motion. An oscillatory time dependent flux is being imposed on then peristaltic flow. Choosing the cartesian coordinate system $O(x, y)$, the flexible walls are represented by

$$y = \pm a_0 s[X - ct / \lambda]$$

Where ‘ a_0 ’ is the wave amplitude, ‘ c ’ is the wave velocity, ‘ λ ’ is the wave length and ‘ s ’ is an arbitrary function of the normalized axial coordinate $x^* = [X - ct / \lambda]$.

In the case of incompressible fluids when the body forces the body moments are absent, the equations of motion is

$$\rho \frac{DV}{Dt} = [-\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 V - \eta \nabla^4 V]$$

The equations of motion for two-dimensional flow incompressible couple stress fluid in the component form are

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right] = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left[\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right] - \eta \left[\frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial y^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right] = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \left[\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right] - \eta \left[\frac{\partial^4 v}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^4 v}{\partial y^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 v}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

(Suffices t, x, y denote differentiation with respect to the respective variable). (u, v) are the velocity components along $O(x, y)$ directions respectively, ' p ' is the fluid pressure, ' ρ ' is the density of the fluid, ' μ ' is the coefficient of the viscosity, ' η ' is the coefficient of couple stress.

The flow being two-dimensional in view of the incompressibility of the flow using (1) we introduce a stream function ' ψ ' such that

$$u = -\psi_y \text{ \& } v = \psi_x \quad (4)$$

Substituting (4) in (2) and (3) and eliminating p , the governing equations in terms of ' ψ ' reduces to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\nabla^2 \psi] - [\psi_y \nabla^2 \psi_x] + [\psi_x \nabla^2 \psi_y] = \frac{\mu}{\rho} [\nabla^4 \psi] - \frac{\eta}{\rho} [\nabla^6 \psi] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Where } \nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$$

The relevant conditions on ψ are

$$\psi_x = 0 \text{ ; } \psi_{y,y} = 0 \quad \text{on } y = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\psi = \psi_f [1 + ke^{i\alpha t}] - a_0 cs \quad \text{on } y = \pm a_0 s [x] \quad (7)$$

$$\psi_{y,yy} = 0 \quad \text{on } y = \pm a_0 s [x] \quad (8)$$

(6) guarantees the vanishing of the transverse flow on the axis of channel in view of the symmetry. (7) corresponds to the no slip of the axial velocity on the channel and also guarantees the assumption of the imposed oscillatory flux across the channel. (8) is the boundary condition related to couple stress fluids.

We define the following non-dimensional variables

$$x^* = [X - ct / \lambda]; \quad y^* = \left[\frac{Y}{a_0} \right]; \quad t^* = [\omega t]$$

$$\psi^* = \left[\frac{\psi}{a_0 c} \right]; \quad \psi_f^* = \left[\frac{\psi_f}{a_0 c} \right]; \quad \varepsilon = \left[\frac{a_0}{\lambda} \right]$$

Introducing these non- dimensional variables in (5) the governing equation in terms of ψ reduces to (on dropping the asterisks)

$$R\varepsilon^3 \left[\psi_{xxx} + \psi_y \psi_{xxx} - \psi_x \psi_{xxy} \right] + \left[R\varepsilon \psi_{xyy} + R\varepsilon \psi_y \psi_{xyy} - R\varepsilon \psi_x \psi_{yyy} \right]$$

$$\left[-SR\varepsilon^6 \psi_{xxxxxx} - SR\psi_{yyyyyy} - 3RS\varepsilon^4 \psi_{xxxxyy} - 3RS\varepsilon^2 \psi_{xxyyyy} \right]$$

$$= \left[-\varepsilon^4 \psi_{xxxx} - \psi_{yyyy} - 2\varepsilon^2 \psi_{xxyy} \right] \tag{9}$$

Where $R = \frac{\rho c a_0}{\mu}$, Reynolds number

$S = \frac{\eta}{\rho c a_0^3}$, Couple stress parameter

The boundary conditions in non-dimensional form are

$$\psi = 1 - S[x] \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x] \tag{10}$$

$$\psi_x = 0; \psi_{yy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0 \tag{11}$$

$$\psi_{yyy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x] \tag{12}$$

3 SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM

Under long wave length assumption ($\varepsilon \ll 1$) keeping in view of the condition (10) ψ may be assumed in the form

$$\psi = \left[\psi_0 + k e^{it} \bar{\psi}_0 \right] + \varepsilon \left[\psi_1 + k e^{it} \bar{\psi}_1 \right] \tag{13}$$

Substituting (13) in (9) and equating the like powers of ε , the equations corresponding to the zeroth and first order steady components are

$$RS \psi_{0yy yyy y} - \psi_{0y y y y} = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$RS \psi_{1y y y y y} - \psi_{1y y y y} = R \left[\psi_{0x y y} + \psi_{0y} \psi_{0x y y} - \psi_{0x} \psi_{0y y y} \right] \quad (15)$$

The conditions to be satisfied by ψ_0 and ψ_1 are

$$\psi_0 = 1 - S[x] \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x]; \quad \psi_1 = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x] \quad (16)$$

$$\psi_{0x} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0; \quad \psi_{1x} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$\psi_{0yy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0; \quad \psi_{1yy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\psi_{0y y y} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x]; \quad \psi_{1y y y} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S(x) \quad (19)$$

Similarly the equations related to zeroth and first order steady components are

$$RS \bar{\psi}_{0y y y y y} - \bar{\psi}_{0y y y y} = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$RS \bar{\psi}_{1y y y y y} - \bar{\psi}_{1y y y y} = R \left[\bar{\psi}_{0x y y} + \bar{\psi}_{0y} \psi_{0x y y} + \psi_{0y} \bar{\psi}_{0x y y} \right] + \\ R \left[-\psi_{0x} \bar{\psi}_{0y y y} - \bar{\psi}_{0x} \psi_{0y y y} \right] \quad (21)$$

The conditions to be satisfied by $\bar{\psi}_0$ and $\bar{\psi}_1$ are

$$\bar{\psi}_0 = 1 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x]; \quad \bar{\psi}_1 = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x] \quad (22)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_{0x} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0; \quad \bar{\psi}_{1x} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_{0yy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0; \quad \bar{\psi}_{1yy} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_{0y y y} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S[x]; \quad \bar{\psi}_{1y y y} = 0 \quad \text{on} \quad y = \pm S(x) \quad (25)$$

Solving (14) and (15) subject to the conditions (16-19), we obtain

$$\psi_0 = G_1 - G_2 y^2 + G_3 Ch [ty] \quad (26)$$

$$\psi_1 = G_4 + G_5 y + G_6 y^2 + G_7 Ch [ty] + G_8 \quad (27)$$

Similarly solving (20) and (21) subject to the boundary conditions (22-25), we get

$$\bar{\psi}_0 = G_9 + G_{10} y^2 + G_{11} Ch[ty] \tag{28}$$

$$\bar{\psi}_1 = G_{12} + G_{13} y + G_{14} y^2 + G_{15} Ch[ty] + G_{16} \tag{29}$$

Solving these equations the constants $G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4,$ and G_5 etc can be obtained

4 SHEAR STRESS AND FLUX

The shear stress at the upper wall $y = s(x)$, in the dimensional form is given by

$$T = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right] \left[1 - \left(\frac{ds}{dx} \right)^2 \right] + \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right] \left[\frac{ds}{dx} \right]}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{ds}{dx} \right)^2 \right]} \text{ and is given by}$$

$$\tau = \frac{\frac{1}{2} [A + B] [1 - m^2] + [C - D] m}{[1 + m^2]}$$

The volume flux of the fluid Q is given by the formula

$$Q = \int_0^s u dy \text{ and is given by}$$

$$Q = \left[\begin{aligned} &G_2 S[x]^2 - G_3 Ch[ts[x]] - hG_{10} S[x]^2 - hG_{11} Ch[ts[x]] - \varepsilon G_5 S[x] - \\ &\varepsilon G_6 S[x]^2 - \varepsilon G_7 Ch[ts[x]] - \varepsilon hG_{13} S[x] - \varepsilon hG_{14} S[x]^2 - \varepsilon hG_{15} Ch[ts[x]] \\ &[-G_3 - \varepsilon G_7 - hG_{11} - \varepsilon hG_{15}] \end{aligned} \right]$$

5 DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The main aim of this paper is to investigate the interaction of pulsatile pressure gradient over a pulsatile flow of a couple stress fluid through flexible boundaries which possibly throw some light on the microcirculation of blood through small vessels. The interaction of flow pattern and the shear stresses has been computationally evaluated for various the governing parameters viz. 'R' the Reynolds Number, 'S' is the couple stress parameter for computational purpose we choose a sinusoidal flexible boundary in the non-dimensional form $y = S(x) = 1 + \beta \cos[x]$. For positive values of β the channel converges as 'x' varies between 0 to Π and

when β is negative the channel diverges in the same limits. The points $x = 0$ and $x = \Pi$ corresponds to points of maximum dilation and constriction respectively or vice versa according as β is positive or negative. To begin with we discuss the phenomenon of flow separation in this peristaltic flow on which an oscillatory time dependent flux being imposed resulting in the pulsatile nature of the flow separation in oscillation flows can be defined as commencing with the initial occurrence of zero velocity or reversed flow at some points in the velocity profile throughout the entire cycle of oscillations. A suitable criterion for the recognition of separation has studied by Despered & Miller [4] is that the velocity gradient of the wall should less than or equal to zero throughout the entire cycle of oscillations. This amounts to the existence of a points at which the shear stress at the wall is observed for the first time to be less than or equal to zero throughout the entire cycle of oscillations. We use this criterion to this separation in this problem. The shear stress on the upper flexible wall is evaluated throughout the cycle of oscillations at different points within a wavelength for different sets of parameters. Fig 1 to 8 we observe from fig 1 to 2 for lower values of $R \leq 10$ and $S = 0.2$ no separation occurs in the flow filed this is because that the shear stress on the wall does not vanish or become negative in a wavelength throughout entire cycle of oscillations. This is true even if $S \leq 0.3$ as long as $R \leq 5$ (Fig 3&4). The flow separation is observed for moderate values of $R \geq 10$ in case of $S \geq 0.4$ (Fig 5&6). However, when $R \geq 20$ even at $S = 0.2$, separation occurs in the flow field (Fig 7 & 8).

We now discuss the behaviour of axial and transverse velocities for various in the governing parameters R & S etc. Fig 9 and 10 corresponds to the axial & transverse velocity profiles for smaller values of $R \leq 15$ & $S = 0.2$ in both converging and diverging parts of the flexible channel. The analysis of axial & transverse velocity at given cross section in both constricted (converging) and dilated (diverging) parts of the channel (Fig 9 & 10) reveals no separation in the flow pattern. Fig 11&12 corresponds axial & transverse velocity profiles for $R \geq 20$ & $S = 0.2$ it is interesting to observe that the separation in the flow pattern occurs with flow taking place in the anti-clockwise sense in the constricted parts and the clockwise sense in the dilated parts in contrast to the earlier case. When $R > 20$ & $S = 0.2$. The resultant velocity in the constricted case is towards the boundary with the phase difference of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ while it is towards to the mid-axis in the dilated part with the same phase difference. Fig 13 & 14 corresponds to the velocity profiles at the higher values of $R = 20$ for variation in S . As already indicated the flow separation takes place at all these values with fluid moving towards boundary in the clockwise sense in the constricted case and towards the axes in the anticlockwise sense in the dilated case. We now discuss the behaviour the magnitude of the velocity components with variation in R & S . For fixing S an increasing R through smaller values ($R \leq 15$) we notice that the axial velocity with increase in R both in the constricted & dilated parts, except vicinity at the boundary in the constricted part, where its magnitude reduces slightly with increasing R (Fig 9). However for higher values of $R \geq 20$ the magnitude of the axial velocity increases rapidly with increase in R everywhere in the channel (Fig 11). The Shear Stresses on the flexible wall for evaluated for various R & S at given axial position. We observe that the Shear Stresses decrease in magnitude for an increase in S or R .

Figure 1: Shear stresses τ for $R=5, S=0.2, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 2: Shear stresses τ for $R=10, S=0.2, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 3: Shear stresses τ for $R=5, S=0.3, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 4: Shear stresses τ for $R=10, S=0.4, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 5: Shear stresses τ for $R=10, S=0.5, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 6: Shear stresses τ for $R=20, S=0.2, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 7: Shear stresses τ for $R=30, S=0.2, \beta=0.005, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, y=1.0043$

	I	II	III	IV	V
t	0	$\frac{\pi}{4}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{3\pi}{4}$	π

Figure 8: u with R when $S=0.2, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	5	10	15	5	10	15
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Figure 9: v with R when $S=0.2, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	5	10	15	5	10	15
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Figure 10: u with R when $S=0.2, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	20	30	40	20	30	40
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Figure 11: v with R when $S=0.2, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	20	30	40	20	30	40
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Figure 12: u with S when $R=20, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
S	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.4
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Figure 13: v with S when $R=20, P=1, C=0.01, k=0.1, x = t = \frac{\pi}{6}$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
S	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.4
B	0.005	0.005	0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005

Table 1: SHEAR STRESS AT THE UPPER WALL (τ)
 $y = 1.0043301, t = \Pi\sqrt{2}, x = 2.355, \beta = 0.005$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
	-0.023314	-0.022917	-0.024648	-0.035522	-0.129348	-0.4304

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	15	15	15	20	30	40
S	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4

Table 2: FLUID FLUX (Q)
 $t = \Pi\sqrt{2}, x = 2.355, \beta = 0.005$

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
	-0.000019	-0.000029	-0.000039	-0.000052	-0.000079	-0.0001

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
R	15	15	15	20	30	40
S	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4

REFERENCES

- Abd El Hakeem Abd El Naby, El Misery AE.M and Abd El Kareem M F (2006). Effects of a magnetic field on trapping through peristaltic motion for generalize Newtonian fluid in a channel. *Physica A*, 367, pp. 79.
- Boyarsky S, Cottschalk C W, Tanagho E A and Zimskind P (1971). *Urodynamics*, Academic Press, New York.
- Burns J C and Parkes T (1967). *J.Fluid Mech*, 29, pp.73.
- Despard R A and Miller J A (1971). *J.Fluid Mech*, 47, pp. 21.
- El Shehawey E F, Mekhemer Kh.S (1994). Couple-stresses in peristaltic transport of Fluids. *J.Phys.D: Appl.Phys*, 27, pp. 1163.
- Eldabe N T M, El-Sayed M F, Ghaly AY and Sayed H M (2007). Peristaltically induced transport of a MHD biviscosity fluid in a non-uniform tube. *Physica A*, 383 (2), pp. 253-266.
- Fung Y C and Yih C S (1969). *J.Fluid Mech*, 37, pp. 579.
- Gachtgens P A (1970). *Pflugers Arch. Ges. Physiol*, 316, pp. 14.
- Hayat T and Ali N (2006). On mechanism of peristaltic flows for power-law fluids. *PhysicaA*, 371, pp. 188.
- Hayat T, Ali N and Asghar S (2007). Hall effects on peristaltic flow of a Maxwell fluid in a porous medium. *Phys.Lett.A*, 363, pp. 397.
- Hayat T, Masood Khan, Siddiqui A M Hutter K and Asghar S (2007). Non-linear peristaltic flow of a Non-Newtonian fluid under effect of a magnetic field in a planner channel. *Commun.Nonlinear Sci. Number.Simul*, 12, pp.910.
- Hayat T, Wang Y, Siddiqui A M, Hutter K and Asghar S (2002). Peristaltic transport of a third-order fluid in a circular cylindrical tube. *Math. Models Appl.Sci*, 12, pp.1691.
- Intaglietta M (1971). *Proc.VIConf.microcirculation*, Karger, Basel.
- Latham TW (1966). M S Thesis, *Massachusetts Instof technology*, Cambridge.
- Latham TW and Shapiro A M (1966). *Proc.Ann.Conf Engg Med. Bio. VB*, pp.147.
- Mekhemer Kh.S (2003). Non-linear peristaltic transport through porous medium in an inclined planner channel. *Porous Medium*, 6, pp. 89.
- Mekhemer Kh.S (2003). Non-linear peristaltic transport through porous medium in an inclined planner channel. *AJSE*, 28 (2A), pp. 183.

- Mekheimer Kh.S, Al-Arabi T H (2003). Non-linear peristaltic transport of MHD flow through porous medium. *Int. J. Math.Sci*, 26, pp. 1663.
- Mekheimer Kh.S, El Shehawey E F, Elaw AM (1998). Peristaltic motion of a particle- fluid suspension in a planner channel. *Internat. J. Theoret. Phy*, 37, pp. 2895.
- Mishra, Ramachandra Rao A (2003). Peristaltic transport of a Newtonian fluid in an asymmetric channel. *ZAMP*, 53, pp. 532.
- Mitra T K and Prasad S N (1974). *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology*, 36, pp. 127.
- Ramachandra R A and Usha S (1995). Peristaltic transport of two immiscible viscous fluids in a circular tube. *J.Fluid Mech*, 298, pp. 271.
- Rappaport M B, Block E H and Irwin J W (1959). *J.Applied.Physiol*, 14, pp. 651.
- Rart H J (1980). Peristaltische Stromungen.*Springer-Verlag*, Berlin.
- Shapiro A H, Jaffrin M Y and Weinberg S L (1969). Peristaltic pumping with long wavelength at low Reynolds number. *Fluid Mech*, 37, pp. 799-825.
- Srivastava L.M (1986). Peristaltic transport of a couple-stress fluid. *Rheol. Acta*, 25, pp.641.
- Srivastava L M and Srivastava V P (1988). *Rheol. Acta*, 27, pp. 428.
- Srivastava V P and Saxena M (1995). A two-fluid modal of non-Newtonian blood flow induced by peristaltic waves. *Rheol. Acta*, 34, pp.406.
- Tsiklauri D, Beresnev I (2001). Non-Newtonian effects in the peristaltic flow of a Maxwell fluid. *Phys.Rev.E*, 64, pp.036303
- Vajravelu K, Sreenadh S and Babu V R (2005). Peristaltic transport of a Herschel-Bulkley fluid in an inclined tube. *Internat. J. Non-Liner Mech*, 40, pp. 83.
- Wilson and Perel (1979). *Pro.of the ASME Bio-Engg.Sym*, New York.